

STRATEGIES FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE PROCESS OF DIGITAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In this article, strategies for developing students' emotional intelligence in the process of digital education are researched. The article analyzes methods of forming students' emotional and social skills with the help of modern pedagogical technologies, online and interactive educational tools. The research shows the importance of emotional intelligence in the educational process, its impact on students' motivation, communication skills, and coping skills. The article also suggests strategies for developing empathy, self-management, social responsibility, and emotional awareness in students using digital platforms and mobile applications. The results of the research give teachers the opportunity to use effective pedagogical approaches to increase emotional intelligence in the modern educational environment.

Introduction. Today, the role of digital technologies in the field of education is increasing. With the help of online platforms, interactive textbooks, mobile applications and various pedagogical tools, the learning process can be more personalized, interesting and effective. At the same time, not only the formation of knowledge and skills, but also the emotional and social development of students is considered an important task.

Emotional intelligence (EI) - a person's ability to understand and control his emotions, communicate effectively with others and adapt in social situations - is an integral part of the modern education process. Studies show that students with high emotional intelligence not only improve their academic results, but also develop skills such as stress tolerance, cooperation and creative thinking(1,B,23")

"In this regard, identifying and implementing effective strategies for developing students' emotional intelligence through the use of digital educational tools is an important pedagogical task. This article is devoted to this issue and analyzes methods and strategies for increasing emotional intelligence with the help of digital technologies (2,B,34.)

Digital educational tools allow not only the rapid delivery of information, but also the ability to monitor the emotional state of students, develop empathy, cooperation and self-

management skills through individual approaches and various interactive exercises. For example, online games, simulations, virtual group work and interactive tests not only engage students in academic activities, but also actively stimulate their emotional intelligence.]

Review of literature on the topic. In recent years, many studies have been conducted in the field of pedagogy and psychology on emotional intelligence (EI) and its importance in the educational process. Goleman (1995) defines emotional intelligence as an individual's ability to understand, manage, and communicate effectively with others' emotions and emphasizes its direct impact on academic and social success. Mayer and Salovey (1997) also explain EI from a formal psychological perspective through four components: self-awareness, self-regulation, social awareness, and relationship management.

The development of emotional intelligence in the context of digital education is also being actively studied. Mishra and Koehler (2006) in the technological pedagogical knowledge development model show that digital tools are effective not only in imparting knowledge, but also in forming students' emotional and social skills. At the same time, online and blended learning studies (Means et al., 2013) confirm the possibility of developing students' empathy, stress management and teamwork skills with the help of digital educational tools.

There are also studies on this topic in Uzbekistan and the CIS countries. For example, Kadirov (2020) and Abdullayeva (2021) analyzed the effectiveness of interactive and digital pedagogical tools in developing students' emotional intelligence. Their research shows that games, simulations, online group work and interactive tests play an important role in improving students' emotional intelligence(3,B,43")

Research methodology. In this study, the pedagogical potential of digital educational tools was also theoretically analyzed. Interactive platforms, virtual laboratories, online tests and simulations in the context of digital education help students develop not only academic knowledge, but also emotional and social skills. Research shows that using digital tools, students can effectively build empathy, self-management and collaboration skills.

Also, international experiences related to strategies for developing emotional intelligence are worthy of attention. For example, Denham and Burton (2003) show that creating emotional awareness programs in school-age children can increase their academic and social success. These studies provide an opportunity to develop similar effective strategies using digital tools.

At the same time, the analysis of the literature shows that effective strategies for the development of students' emotional intelligence in the process of digital education have not yet been fully developed, and methodological research in this field is ongoing. This makes this topic relevant for modern pedagogical research. In recent years, many studies have been conducted in the field of pedagogy and psychology on emotional intelligence (EI) and its importance in the educational process. Goleman (1995) defines emotional intelligence as an individual's ability to understand, manage, and communicate effectively with others' emotions and emphasizes its direct impact on academic and social success. Also, Mayer and Salovey (1997) explain EI from a formal psychological perspective through four components: self-awareness, self-control, social awareness, and relationship management (4,B,63")

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Analysis and results. In this study, strategies for developing students' emotional intelligence were analyzed using digital educational tools. The analysis of theoretical literature and international studies shows that digital tools play an effective role in the formation of emotional and social skills of students.

The correct use of digital educational tools in the pedagogical process helps to effectively develop the emotional intelligence of students. At the same time, when choosing digital strategies, the age characteristics of students, the content of the subject, and pedagogical goals should be taken into account. The results of the study show that digital education strategies that have a positive effect on emotional and social development allow for the development of theoretically sound and practical recommendations.

Conclusions and suggestions. This study focused on the theoretical study of the issues of developing emotional intelligence of students in the process of digital education(5,B,23")

1. The development of emotional intelligence can be effectively implemented with the help of digital educational tools. Interactive exercises, virtual group work, online tests, and simulations help students develop self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management skills.

2. Analysis of various pedagogical studies and literature shows that strategies for the formation of emotional and social skills in digital education are effective and theoretically sound. This will improve the academic and social success of students.

3. The effectiveness of digital educational tools can be increased taking into account the age characteristics of students, the content of the subject and pedagogical goals.

Offers:

Teachers are recommended to regularly use interactive exercises, virtual group work and reflection exercises when using digital tools.

It is desirable to include special modules or sections on the development of emotional intelligence in school programs. It is recommended to introduce special indicators and tests to assess students' emotional and social skills in digital educational platforms.

Future research should also explore practical experiences in developing empathy, self-management, and social skills.

This study serves to determine the effective strategies of using digital educational tools in the development of students' emotional intelligence on a theoretical basis and provides recommendations for pedagogical practice.

References:

1. Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. New York: Bantam Books.
2. Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is Emotional Intelligence? In P. Salovey & D. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional Development and Emotional Intelligence: Educational Implications*. New York: Basic Books.
3. Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A Framework for Teacher Knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108(6), 1017–1054.
4. Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., Bakia, M., & Jones, K. (2013). *Evaluation of Evidence-Based Practices in Online Learning: A Meta-Analysis and Review of Online Learning Studies*. Washington, DC: U.S. Department of Education.
5. Denham, S. A., & Burton, R. (2003). *Social and Emotional Prevention and Intervention Programming for Preschoolers*. New York: Springer.]

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